

*Bst*YI, two fragments of about 700 bp and 300 bp were observed. Sequence analysis of the CP1-2 region from RTSV-Vt6 (unpublished results) confirmed the absence of the *Hind*III site and the presence of three fragments after *Bst*YI digestion: 707 bp, 284 bp, and 108 bp. Variation between the two viral strains was confirmed at nt positions 2556 and 3032 based on the published sequence. The RT-PCR method can therefore be used to study RTSV coat protein variation in natural field populations.

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Mechanism of resistance to rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV)

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RTSV is one of two viruses that cause tungro disease. RTSV is independently transmitted, whereas the other virus, rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV), is dependent on RTSV for its transmission by the green leafhopper (GLH), *Nephotettix virescens*. The occurrence and spread of tungro disease therefore depend on the presence of RTSV in the field. Resistance to RTSV infection would slow down the spread of the disease.

One of the most important components of a tungro management strategy has been the use of resistant varieties. After a few years of intensive cultivation, however, these varieties succumb to tungro infection. Changes in field response to tungro infection have been

attributed to a shift in GLH virulence to the varieties over time as shown by experiments conducted under natural and artificial conditions (Dahal 1988, Dahal et al 1990, Cabunagan and Ling 1982). Although these studies indicate that the mechanism of resistance to tungro might be vector-dependent, other results showed a different phenomenon. For example, GLH selected on Pankhari 203, TAPL 796, and IR20 for 9-19 generations did not cause a significant increase in RTSV transmission to these varieties (Heinrich and Rapusas 1984, Dahal 1988, Hibino et al 1988). Hence, the mechanism of resistance to tungro may not be vector-dependent only and GLH adaptation may not be the only factor involved in resistance breakdown.

In 1995, a new strain of RTSV, designated as Vt6, was isolated from rice variety TKM6 in Midsayap, North Cotabato, Philippines (Cabauatan et al 1995). TKM6 is highly resistant to the IRRI strain of RTSV (strain A) and is the common parent of IR20, IR26, IR30, and IR40. These varieties have moderate resistance to GLH and have shown consistent resistance to RTSV since they were released in the 1970s (Hibino et al 1988). We used IR26 to study the role of GLH adaptation and strain variation in the mechanism of resistance to RTSV and found that resistance to RTSV is both vector- and virus-dependent. GLHs were collected from a field in Polangui, Albay, Philippines, and reared on rice variety TN1 for two generations. The progenies were then

tested for their transmission of RTSV strains A and Vt6 to TN1 (RTSV-susceptible) and IR26 (RTSV-resistant). Afterwards, the GLH colony was divided into two; one-half was reared on TN1 (GLH-susceptible) and the other half on IR26 (GLH-resistant) for 11 generations. The GLH colonies were then tested again for RTSV strain transmission on both TN1 and IR26. Transmission of RTSV strains A and Vt6 by each GLH colony was compared on both varieties before and after selection. RTSV transmission efficiency of selected colonies was also tested on rice varieties TKM6 and Adday Sel., varieties with known resistance to RTSV. All transmission tests were conducted in test tubes at 1 insect seedling⁻¹ for an overnight inoculation access. RTSV was detected in inoculated plants by the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA).

After 11 generations, the GLH colony on IR26 reproduced as well as the one on TN1. It was reported that a biotype of GLH could be selected by being reared on a resistant rice variety (Kobayashi et al 1983); therefore, the GLH colony on IR26 can be considered to be adapted to its host. Transmission tests showed that the reaction of IR26 to RTSV-Vt6 changed from resistant (23% infection rate before selection) to susceptible (62.8% infection rate after 11 generations on IR26), while the reaction of IR26 to RTSV-A remained resistant (0% infection rate) (Table 1).

These results indicate that the resistance of IR26 to RTSV is both

Table 1. Transmission (%) of RTSV strains A and Vt6 to IR26 and TN1 by field-collected GLH before selection on IR26, TN1, TKM6, and Adday Sel. and after selection for 11 generations.

Variety	Before selection ^b		After selection on			
	AC	Vt6 ^c	TN1		IR26	
			A	Vt6	A	Vt6
TN1	97	78	82	82	59	82
IR26	0	23	0	29	0	63
TKM6	-	- ^d	0	59	0	31
Adday Sel.	-	-	0	0	0	0

^aOne insect seedling⁻¹, overnight inoculation access; 40 seedlings treatment⁻¹. ^bField-collected (Bicol) GLH was reared on TN1 for two generations and adult progenies were tested for transmission of RTSV A and Vt6 before selection on IR26. ^cTested by ELISA 3 wk after inoculation. ^dNot tested.

vector- and virus-dependent. In the presence of a resistance-breaking strain, such as Vt6, a shift in GLH virulence (adaptation) results in a breakdown of resistance. On the other hand, the resistance of IR26 did not break down in the presence of RTSV-A. Selection of GLH on this variety for 11 generations did not result in increased RTSV-A infection. TN1 is susceptible to both virus strains regardless of the GLH colony used for inoculation. TKM6 is a differential host for both strains. Although the selected colonies did not transmit RTSV-A, they transmitted RTSV-Vt6 at varying efficiency, depending on the GLH colony used. Variety Adday Sel. (IRGC Acc. No. 180) was highly resistant to both strains regardless of the GLH colony used. Table 2 summarizes the mechanism of resistance of IR26 to RTSV.

This study demonstrated that breakdown of resistance to tungro disease can be both virus- and vector-dependent. This study also showed that some rice cultivars have "true"

Table 2. Mechanism of resistance of IR26 to RTSV.

Virus strain	GLH colony	Reaction	Mechanism of resistance
RTSV-A	Nonadapted	Resistant	R to both virus and vector
RTSV-A	Adapted	Resistant	R to virus
RTSV-Vt6	Nonadapted	Resistant	R to vector
RTSV-Vt6	Adapted	Susceptible	

resistance, that is, race-specific resistance, to the virus strain(s) as exhibited by IR26 and TKM6 against RTSV-A and Adday Sel. against both RTSV strains. This information should be considered when formulating effective control strategies against tungro.

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Seed technology

Leaf number: a reliable parameter for determining seeding intervals between parental lines in hybrid rice seed production

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Because parental lines of rice hybrids usually differ in their growth duration, obtaining well-synchronized flowering is a major problem in hybrid rice seed production. The present method of staggered sowing of parental lines based on their growth duration difference, though simple, is not always effective, especially in areas where temperature changes are frequent. Reports from China indicate that because the leaf number of a rice

cultivar is fairly stable, leaf number difference can be used to decide the seeding dates of parental lines in hybrid rice seed production. Before using this method, however, the leaf number of the prospective parental lines to be used in hybrid rice seed production should be ascertained. We conducted an experiment to determine the leaf number of two cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines and five promising restorers during the 1994 wet season (WS), 1995 WS, and 1995 dry season (DS) at the DRR research farm. We also compared the extent of variation for leaf number and days to flowering over the seasons.

Seedlings were raised in wet beds, 10 seedlings were marked, and leaf counting started from the tenth day. After 25 d, the same seedlings were transplanted to the main field and leaves were counted at intervals of 5 d

until the opening of the flag leaf. Incomplete leaves were numbered by comparing their length with the previous leaf, using a 10-point scale (see figure).

The table presents data for leaf number and days to 50% flowering. Leaf number ranged from 15.3 (IR58025A) to 18.5 (Vajram). The coefficient of variation for leaf number over seasons varied from 0.65 to 1.89 and a wide range of variation was observed for growth duration (CV 6.23-12.53). Variation for leaf number between WS and DS was negligible, whereas growth duration varied widely between the two seasons. In view of the relative stability of leaf number over seasons, this parameter can be used to determine the seeding intervals between parental lines to obtain better synchronization in flowering.